

Octopus Choreographies

Small-scale Fisheries in Angeiras, Portugal

Fishing Architecture

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Between 22 and 27 September 2024, the Fishing Architecture research team conducted a workshop to develop its methodologies focusing on the small-scale fisheries community of Angeiras, in the north of Portugal. This comic is the first instalment of a series to bring these fisheries choreographies to a wider audience. Drawings were authored by Raquel Silva who developed the storytelling with André Tavares and Rafael Sousa Santos, who wrote the texts. Research is indebted to the workshop team, as well as the 2023 preceding workshop, who also included Alice Nouvet, Daniel Duarte Pereira, José Pedro Fernandes, Patrícia Reis and Inês Guilherme.

2024 workshop team: André Tavares, Rafael Sousa Santos, Sónia Gabriel, Garðar Eyjólfsson, Cláudia Soares, Lise Freitas, Will Gibbs, Mafalda Rangel, João Pontes, Teresa Alexandre, Elsa Froufe, Mónica Felício, Diana Feijó, Alberto Rocha, Manuel Nande, André Machado, Diego Inglez de Souza, Letícia Carmo, Hon Chio Lai, and Livia Sinigaglia, with the special participation of Cristina Brito, Patrícia Carvalho, Brígida Baptista, and Anatole Danto. We are indebted to the fishing community of Angeiras, who welcomed our enquiries with unwavering patience and generosity.

The fishing community of Angeiras is a case study that gives a sense of the complex relationship between marine ecosystems and coastal architecture. In functional terms, its characteristic stone houses, built near the beach, are used in conjunction with vessels operating small-scale fisheries that target a variety of species including pouting, sea bass, shrimp, lobster, and octopus (*Octopus vulgaris*). This workshop focused on octopus catches as a means to collect and represent a variety of scientific and architectural data. The work was divided into three areas: the sea, the shore, and the market. In the sea section, the natural environment of the species was addressed, with a focus on how octopus are trapped in fishing gear, and how the fisherfolk use their tackle. The shore section looked at the deployment of the boats, and how the equipment is disposed in relation to the buildings that support the operations. In the market section, attention was paid to the weight of the catches, their commercial value, and the relationship with other fisheries. In the three areas, octopus and fisherfolk move in unique choreographies that were scrutinized. The facts and figures were recorded in various ways at every stage of the fishing process, with drawings used to interlink the resulting narratives, producing a comprehensive description of the ongoing dynamics both on land and at the sea.

Keywords: Octopus; Small-scale fisheries; Fishing community; Fishing architecture

ANGEIRAS IS A COASTAL COMMUNITY THAT EVOLVED OVER THE COURSE OF THE TWENTIETH CENTURY, WITH ITS SMALL-SCALE FISHING PRACTICES, USING RELATIVELY SMALL BOATS. THERE IS AN INTIMATE CONNECTION BETWEEN THE HOUSES, CONSTRUCTED TO SUPPORT FISHERIES, THE BOATS, AND THE MARINE ECOSYSTEMS THAT PROVIDE RESOURCES. THIS PLACE DEMONSTRATES A CLOSE-KNIT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE BUILT ENVIRONMENT AND ITS NEIGHBOURING UNDERWATER LANDSCAPES. THIS IS WHERE FISHING ARCHITECTURE BEGINS!

JUST OFFSHORE, THE SEABED PROVIDES A UNIQUE CONTEXT FOR A VARIETY OF SPECIES TO THRIVE IN. A STRONG UPWELLING AND RELATIVELY SHALLOW WATERS WITH A GRANITE SUBSTRATE CREATE DIVERSE HABITATS, INCLUDING KELP FORESTS, SABELLARIA REEFS, AND SANDY BOTTOMS. THIS MIX BRINGS IN WAVES OF NUTRIENTS, ENOUGH TO FEED A WIDE VARIETY OF SPECIES THAT BECOME INTERCONNECTED. IN THE CONTACT AREAS BETWEEN THESE HABITATS, IT IS COMMON TO FIND MANY SPECIES WITH COMMERCIAL VALUE, WHICH FISHERFOLK CAPTURE TO EARN THEIR LIVING AND NURTURE A SENSE OF COMMUNITY.

IN THE KELP FORESTS (1), ONE MIGHT FIND *LAMINARIA HYPERBOREA*, *SACCORHIZA POLYSCHIDES*, *CHONDRUS CRISPUS*, *CODIUM TOMENTOSUM*, AND *PALMARIA PALMATA*. AMONG THE REEFS AND ROCKY CREVICES LURK THE CONGER EEL, *CONGER CONGER* (2) AND THE CLEVER OCTOPUS, *OCTOPUS VULGARIS* (3). THE OPEN WATERS BRING IN THE SWIFT SEABASS, *DICENTRARCHUS LABRAX* (4) AND THE STRIPED POUTING *TRISOPTERUS LUSCUS* (5). ON THE SEABED, SEA URCHINS *PARACENTROTUS LIVIDUS* (6) GRAZE, WHILE VELVET CRABS *NECORA PUBER* (7) SCURRY THROUGH THE DETRITUS.

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DEPARTING FROM ANGEIRAS BEFORE DAWN, FISHERS CAN NAVIGATE OUT TO THE SIX-MILE LIMIT, WHERE THEY LAUNCH THEIR GEAR IN CAREFULLY CHOSEN SPOTS. THE PLACES, WHICH ARE NEGOTIATED ACROSS THE COMMUNITY, OFTEN BELONG TO SPECIFIC VESSELS--UNOFFICIAL, BUT RESPECTED! IT'S A TRUE FORM OF SEA TERRITORIALIZATION. IN FACT, THESE TERRITORIES CORRESPOND TO THE NATURE OF SEABED AND UNDERWATER ECOSYSTEMS, WHERE THE CHARACTERISTICS OF DIFFERENT AREAS BENEFIT DIFFERENT SPECIES. AND WHEN YOU SPOT TINY SWIRLS IN A VESSEL'S TRACK? THAT'S THE MOMENT THE ENGINE WAS CUT, AND THE BOAT WAS LEFT TO DRIFT WITH THE CURRENT WHILE THE GEAR WAS PUT TO WORK.

HERE, WE HAVE TWO SETS OF TRAJECTORIES--ONE MAINLY FOR SEABASS, THE OTHER FOR OCTOPUS. BOTH START FROM ANGEIRAS (1), GO NEARBY LEIXÕES (2), AND HEAD TOWARD FAMILIAR FISHING SPOTS: ONE TYPICALLY USED FOR CATCHING SEABASS (3), THE OTHER KNOWN AS A RELIABLE OCTOPUS GROUND (4).

1. OCTOPUSES THRIVE ON THE NATURALLY ROCKY, SANDY AND IN MUDDY SEABED AREAS, WHERE TASTY CRABS ARE EASY TO FIND.

2. FISHING BOATS, 8 TO 10 METRES IN LENGTH, ARE EQUIPPED WITH ENGINES, ECHO SOUNDERS, GPS, AND OTHER DEVICES, READY TO NAVIGATE OFFSHORE.

3. POTS ARE SET ALONG A LINE, WITH AN ANCHOR ON ONE END AND A BUOY ON THE OTHER, EACH LINE CARRYING ABOUT A HUNDRED POTS, SPACED 15 METRES APART.

4. OCTOPUSES LOVE THE POTS BECAUSE THEY PROVIDE SHELTER, ESPECIALLY AWAY FROM THE ROCKY SEABED. SOMETIMES FEMALE OCTOPUS EVEN USE THE TRAPS AS A PLACE TO LAY EGGS. OOPS... THESE EGGS WON'T MAKE IT.

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FISHERIES MOSTLY HAPPEN AT NIGHT. OCTOPUSES ARE TAKEN BY SURPRISE AND SNARED WHEN THE POTS ARE HAILED TO THE SURFACE. ON BOARD, THE FISHER GETS TO WORK, HAULING UP THE POTS AND CHECKING EACH POT. SOMETIMES THERE'S AN OCTOPUS INSIDE, SOMETIMES THERE ISN'T. OCTOPUS AND SHRIMP ARE THE TOP CATCHES IN ANGEIRAS, WITH THE HIGHEST COMMERCIAL VALUE, FOLLOWED BY POUTING AND SEA BASS. OCTOPUS CAN BE FISHED YEAR ROUND, BUT SHRIMP IS LIMITED TO THREE MONTHS OWING TO SEASONAL CLOSURES AND THE HARSH WEATHER DURING THE FISHING PERIOD. OCTOPUS AND SHRIMP CATCHES OFTEN ALTERNATE--WHEN ONE DROPS, THE OTHER RISES. OTHER SPECIES, SUCH AS POUTING AND SEA BASS, ARE MORE CONSISTENT.

AS EACH TRAP IS PULLED IN, THE FISHER INSPECTS IT FOR OCTOPUSES. ONCE EMPTIED, THE POTS ARE STACKED FOR THE NEXT ROUND.

THE POTS ARE KEPT IN SEQUENCE, READY TO BE RESET IN REVERSE ONCE THE HAUL IS DONE.

SENSING DANGER, OCTOPUSES CLING ON TIGHT! A QUICK SPRAY OF SALT WATER FROM THE FISHER, AND THE OCTOPUS RELEASES ITS GRIP, STUNNED.

ONLY THE BIG SPECIMENS ARE TAKEN. IF THEY'RE NOT OF SUFFICIENT SIZE, BACK THEY GO IN THE WATER TO GROW.

THE CATCH IS SECURED IN A CAGE, SIMILAR TO A TRAP, DESIGNED TO KEEP THEM PRISONER UNTIL THE BOAT REACHES THE SHORE.

NO PIER? NO PROBLEM! BOATS ARE BEACHED AND PULLED UP BY A TRACTOR, SLIDING UP OVER THE SAND TO THE POSITION WHERE THEY END UP BEING MOORED. NOWADAYS, ANGEIRAS'S FLEET NUMBERS 16 BOATS.

OCTOPUS WAIT ON BOARD ALONGSIDE OTHER CATCHES.

BACK ON SHORE, THE WOMEN OF ANGEIRAS STEP IN. THEY SORT, MANAGE, AND PREPARE THE CATCH TO BE WEIGHED AND SOLD. THEY ALSO NEED TO DEAL WITH OCCASIONAL PEEPS--LIKE US!

IN 2023, 15 TONS OF OCTOPUS WERE LANDED IN ANGEIRAS, ALONG WITH 7 OF SHRIMP, 4 OF POUTING AND 2.5 OF SEA BASS, PLUS SMALLER HAULS OF VELVET CRAB, CONGER, SEA URCHIN, AND SEA BREAM.*

INTO THE AUCTION HOUSE!
EACH CATCH IS WEIGHED,
GRADED, AND PRICED. BEHIND
THE COUNTER, MS. NATÁLIA
LOGS IT ALL FOR DOCAPESCA,
THE NATIONAL AGENCY THAT
OVERSEES FISHERIES TRADE.
SHE MAKES SURE THE
NUMBERS ADD UP AND THE SALE
IS READY TO GO.

IN 2023, 9.5 TONS OF OCTOPUS
WERE LANDED IN ANGEIRAS,
ALONG WITH 5.6 OF SHRIMP, 2.7
OF POUTING AND 1.9 OF SEA
BASS, PLUS SMALLER HAULS OF
CONGER, SEA BREAM, GOOSE
BARNACLES AND VELVET CRAB.
FOR THEIR COMMERCIAL VALUE,
SHRIMP LED THE PACK,
BRINGING IN €71,439, WITH
OCTOPUS CLOSE BEHIND AT
€63,916 AND SEABASS AT
€17,148, FOLLOWED BY POUTING
AT €6,569, CONGER AT €3,307
AND VELVET CRAB AT €2,435.
AVERAGE PRICES AT THE
AUCTION HOUSE? OCTOPUS,
€6.67/KG; SHRIMP, €12.64/KG;
AND SEABASS, €8.79/KG.
SHRIMP HOLDS THE CROWN
FOR THE TOP PRICE!*

* VALUES SOURCED
FROM STATISTICS

FISHING ARCHITECTURE ENDS ONCE
THE ANIMAL IS TRANSFORMED INTO
A COMMODITY. ONCE IT LEAVES THE
AUCTION HOUSE, THE FISHERFOLK
HAVE COMPLETED THE TERRESTRIAL
CYCLE OF RESOURCE EXTRACTION.

Fishing Architecture

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